

1. What is Chemical Looping Combustion?

- No dilution of the fuel-reactor effluent by N_2 with reduced potential for thermal NO_x formation.
- CO_2 -rich stream after H_2O condensation: typically >95 vol% dry [1,4].
- Lower capture energy penalty than conventional CO_2 capture routes [1].
- Fuel-flexible process: gases, liquids, solids, biomass, and waste-derived fuels [1,2].

2. Key Challenge: Soot Formation in the Fuel Reactor

Factors Influencing Soot Formation [1-3]

- Soot formation may induce carbonaceous deposition, oxygen-carrier deactivation, and heat-transfer degradation.
- It can reduce fuel conversion, thermal efficiency, and long-term reactor reliability.
- Its prediction is challenging due to the strong coupling between gas-phase chemistry, soot dynamics, oxidation, and transport.

3. Toward a CFD-oriented framework for optimisation and intensification of CLC reactors

Predictive and CFD-affordable framework for soot formation in CLC reactors.

Scientific challenges

- High-dimensional chemistry-soot systems make direct CFD integration computationally prohibitive.
- Soot formation depends on coupled gas-phase chemistry, inception, growth and oxidation pathways.
- Reducing computational cost while preserving key chemistry-soot feedbacks remains a major modelling challenge.

4. Preliminary Results

- **Soot yield prediction** for the pyrolysis of a 4.0% C_2H_2 -1.0% C_2H_5OH blend in a plug-flow reactor.
- **Model comparison** between the **Gokul** model, the **sectional soot model (SSM)** of Pachano and Aubagnac [5], and the experimental data of Esarte et al. [6].
- **Strong temperature dependence** of soot formation highlighted across the investigated conditions.
- **A first basis for validating** the soot-coupled chemistry model.

Bibliography

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- [2] Zhao, X. et al. *Energy Environ. Sci.* 10 (2017) 1885–1910.
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- [4] Lyngfelt, A. *Oil Gas Sci. Technol.* 66 (2011) 161–172.
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- [6] Esarte, C. et al. *Fuel Process. Technol.* 90 (2009) 496–503.

5. Next Steps

- **Study tar surrogates** under CLC-relevant conditions.
- **Validate the model** against experimental and reference data.
- **Analyse soot sensitivity** to temperature and residence time.
- **Reduce the mechanism** and generate the training database.
- **Train a neural-network surrogate** to replace the kinetic solver.
- **Integrate the surrogate chemistry** into CFD and assess computational speed-up.